

Synthesis and characterisation of palladium(II) and platinum(II) complexes with triphenylphosphine sulphide and triphenylstibine

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Manuscript received 8 August 2007, revised 7 January 2008, accepted 8 January 2008

Abstract : The complexes of palladium(II) and platinum(II) with triphenylphosphine sulphide (Ph₃PS) and triphenylstibine (Ph₃Sb) of composition [ML₂X₂] (M = Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}; L = Ph₃PS or Ph₃Sb and X = Cl, Br, I or SCN) have been prepared and characterized. The triphenylstibine sulphide complexes like former ligand could not be isolated as the ligand get desulphurized in aqueous medium and the complexes of desulphurized ligand triphenylstibine have only been isolated in pure form. The complexes have been characterized by UV, IR, ¹H NMR spectroscopic methods and resembles with square planar geometry.

Keywords : Triphenylphosphine sulphide, triphenylstibine, palladium(II), platinum(II).

Introduction

There have been a large number of informations regarding interaction of DNA with some Pt metal complexes and it leads to the disruption of helix structure of DNA and interfere the replication. The complexes of Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} with adenines, thiamine cytosine and various amino acids interact with DNA and RNA¹. Because of the relevance of phosphorus with DNA in biological system the complexes of phosphorus containing ligand with Pt metals have been studied widely².

In present paper, we report the preparation and characterisation of the complexes of Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} with triphenylstibine and phosphorus containing ligand triphenylphosphine sulphide.

Results and discussion

Attempt was made to prepare complexes of palladium(II) and platinum(II) with Ph₃PS and Ph₃SbS but the complexes of Ph₃SbS like Ph₃PS could not be obtained and instead the complexes of desulphurised Ph₃SbS were obtained in good yield. The elemental analysis of complexes correspond to formula [M(Ph₃P=S)₂X₂] (X = Cl, Br, I or SCN and M = Pd²⁺ or Pt²⁺) and [M(Ph₃Sb)₂X₂] (X = Cl, Br, I or SCN and M = Pd²⁺ or Pt²⁺) (Table 1).

It has been found that triphenylstibine sulphide undergoes desulphurization during complex formation and attempt to isolate Ph₃SbS complexes were unsuccessful.

Table 1

Complex	Elemental analysis (%) :		
	Found (Calcd.)		
	M	C	H
[Pd(Ph ₃ P=S) ₂ Cl ₂]	13.72 (13.98)	56.22 (56.44)	3.70 (3.91)
[Pd(Ph ₃ P=S) ₂ Br ₂]	12.26 (12.45)	50.45 (50.56)	3.34 (3.51)
[Pd(Ph ₃ P=S) ₂ I ₂]	11.01 (11.21)	45.36 (45.55)	3.25 (3.16)
[Pd(Ph ₃ P=S) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	13.04 (13.12)	56.12 (56.26)	3.50 (3.78)
[Pd(Ph ₃ Sb) ₂ Cl ₂]	11.94 (12.05)	48.72 (48.92)	3.25 (3.39)
[Pd(Ph ₃ Sb) ₂ I ₂]	9.68 (9.98)	40.33 (40.52)	2.68 (2.81)
[Pd(Ph ₃ Sb) ₂ Br ₂]	10.74 (10.94)	44.24 (44.44)	2.88 (3.08)
[Pd(Ph ₃ Sb) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	11.36 (11.46)	39.03 (39.14)	3.12 (3.23)
[Pt(Ph ₃ P=S) ₂ Cl ₂]	22.64 (22.84)	50.73 (50.58)	4.14 (3.51)
[Pt(Ph ₃ P=S) ₂ I ₂]	18.62 (18.81)	41.19 (41.15)	2.79 (2.89)
[Pt(Ph ₃ P=S) ₂ Br ₂]	18.71 (18.83)	41.65 (41.71)	3.01 (2.89)
[Pt(Ph ₃ Sb) ₂ Cl ₂]	20.18 (20.07)	44.12 (44.46)	2.95 (3.08)
[Pt(Ph ₃ Sb) ₂ I ₂]	16.55 (16.89)	37.30 (37.40)	2.48 (2.59)
[Pt(Ph ₃ Sb) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	19.08 (19.19)	44.68 (44.87)	2.82 (2.95)

The desulphurization of Ph_3SbS occurred due to inert pair effect and low electronegativity of antimony which stabilizes Sb^{3+} (Ph_3Sb) rather than Sb^{5+} present in ligand Ph_3SbS .

Both Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes were isolated as light yellow to orange or deep brown product. These complexes are insoluble in water but dissolve in ethanol and organic solvents. The qualitative electrical conductance value of complexes in DMF (Λ_{∞} 1.3–3.6 $\Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$) indicated non ionic³ nature suggested anions to be bonded with metal atom. The complexes are diamagnetic indicating four coordinated planar structure of both Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes⁴.

The electronic absorption spectra in chloroform located at 203, 205, 207, 210, 212, 215, 216, 218, 221, 225, 228 and 230 nm in triphenylphosphine sulphide is attributed to $\sigma\text{-}\sigma^*$ as well as $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition of phenyl ring⁵. The strong absorption band at 261 nm in free ligand is attributed to $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition of $\text{P}=\text{S}$ bond. The weak band observed at 328 nm can be attributed to $n\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions. The band at 261 is shifted to higher wavelength in complexes indicated the coordination of ligand with sulphur atom⁶. In addition to electronic transition of ligand molecule, the palladium(II) complexes display one prominent electronic band located at 401–484 nm attributable to $^1A_{1g}\text{-}^1A_{2g}$ transition in planar field⁴. The $d\text{-}d$ transition of Pt^{II} complexes were observed in the region 385 to 410 nm ($^1A_{1g}\text{-}^1A_{2g}$ transition). The electronic transition of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes are inconsistent with four coordinated planar structure⁴.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of triphenylphosphine sulphide display only phenyl ring proton NMR signals as multiplet in the range δ 7.2 and 7.8 ppm. In phenyl ring there are three types of proton with respect to $\text{P}=\text{S}$ group. The hydrogen atoms *ortho* to $\text{P}=\text{S}$ substituent are of two types and these split into two signals each. The NMR signals of *ortho* protons are more de-shielded and observed between δ 7.6–7.8 ppm as quarterate. The protons at *para* position, with respect to $\text{P}=\text{S}$ group are less de-shielded and are observed at δ 7.2–7.4 ppm and appear as triplet. The two protons located at *meta* positions with respect to $\text{P}=\text{S}$ group also appear as triplet (2 adjacent H). Thus *meta* and *para* protons signals are less deshielded and observed as multiplet between δ 7.2 and 7.4 ppm.

The ^1H NMR spectra of triphenylphosphine sulphide (L) complexes $[\text{PdL}_2\text{I}_2]$ and $[\text{PdL}_2(\text{SCN})_2]$ are quite interesting. The *ortho* proton signals of $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{P}=\text{S}$ are observed as quarterate similar to free ligand molecules. If the ligand molecules would have been attached at *cis*

position, the *ortho* proton signals might have appeared as splitted bands. In absence of further splitting of *ortho* proton signals, the *trans* bonding of ligand molecules are suggested in $[\text{PdL}_2\text{X}_2]$. The *para* proton signals of phenyl rings are less de-shielded were observed as quarterate (δ 7.24–7.34 ppm). The *meta* proton signals of phenyl rings are deshielded larger than *para* and observed as triplet (δ 7.70–7.78 ppm). The similar pattern of NMR shift were observed in the NMR spectrum of $[\text{PdL}_2(\text{SCN})_2]$. The low downfield shift is due to steric volume of sulphur of thiocyanate group (SCN) which is bonded to central metal atom as a linear ($-\text{SCN}$) group.

The ^1H NMR signals of $[\text{Pt}(\text{Ph}_3\text{PS})_2\text{I}_2]$ showed larger down field shift for *ortho* phenyl proton (δ 7.8–8.0 ppm). The *meta* and *para* protons in complexes also showed larger shift of proton signals (δ 7.4–7.7 ppm) as quarterate. The proton NMR signals of $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{Sb}$ complexes also display separate NMR signals for *ortho*, *para* and *meta* protons (δ 7.7–7.8 ppm as triplet) and multiplet at δ 7.5–7.6 ppm and downfield shifted from free ligand. No major splitting in *ortho* proton signal indicated the *trans* planar structure of complexes. The proton coupled ^{13}C NMR of tertiary carbon in complexes are shifted to higher δ value (136.76 ppm) while those of *ortho*, *meta* and *para* carbon to lower δ value on coordinations. The absence of splitting of tertiary ^{13}C NMR signal supported *trans* bonding of ligand. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{Sb}$ showed tertiary carbon signal at δ 138.36 ppm which shifted downfield and located near δ 139.43 ppm. The *para* carbon signal at δ 128.57 and 128.85(d) do not shift appreciably while *meta* C signal was observed as singlet (δ 136.218 ppm). The ^{13}C NMR signals of *para*, and *meta* carbon in complexes (δ 127.168, 127.25(d), 128.75 and 129.60(d)) were less affected. The absence of splitting and downfield shifting of tertiary carbon atom signal suggested *trans* coordination of Ph_3Sb in complexes.

In IR spectrum the medium to strong bands observed at 1583, 1479, 1433 and 1332 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of triphenylphosphine sulphide are characteristic of phenyl ring ($\text{C}=\text{C}$) and ($\text{C}-\text{C}$) skeletal vibration. The IR bands at 1307, 1188, 1159 and 1101 are attributed to ($\text{C}-\text{H}$) deformation and ($\text{C}-\text{C}$) stretching vibration of phenyl ring. The IR bands at 1026 and 997 are attributed to $\nu(\text{P}=\text{S})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ vibrations.

The IR spectra of ligands and their complexes display all characteristic vibrations of aromatic ring and aromatic deformation and out of plane bending bands. These vibrations are affected in the complex molecules. The major change that has been observed is the ($\text{P}=\text{S}$) stretching

vibration is the intensity of band at maxima. The $\nu(\text{P}=\text{S})$ of ligand were observed at 1026 cm^{-1} for $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{PS}$ and $(\text{P}-\text{C})$ stretch at 850 cm^{-1} . The complexes display $(\text{P}=\text{S})$ stretches in the range ($985\text{--}997\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The IR spectra of Ph_3Sb palladium(II) complexes display absence of band near 1026 cm^{-1} indicating absence of $(\text{Sb}=\text{S})$ group in Ph_3Sb . A large red shift in the $(\text{P}=\text{S})$ stretching band of triphenylphosphine sulphide can be attributed to bonding of ligand through 'S' atom⁶. In the far IR region the complexes display IR bands of $(\text{M}-\text{L})$ and $(\text{M}-\text{X})$ stretches and observed in the region $400\text{--}220\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The metal halogen stretching band were observed in the range of $200\text{--}390\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $\text{M}-\text{Cl}$ stretching band occurs at $320\text{--}390\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\text{M}-\text{I}$ stretching band near $190\text{--}300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ while the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ band position occurs in the range of $300\text{--}430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region⁷. In present complexes the $\text{M}-\text{X}$ and $\text{M}-\text{L}$ vibrations also occur in the same region of spectrum. In case of thiocyanato complex $[\text{PdL}_2(\text{SCN})_2]$. The $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ vibration were observed as sharp and strong band at 2154 cm^{-1} while $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ at 705 cm^{-1} and $\delta(\text{SCN})$ at 474 which are diagnostic of S-bonded thiocyanate group. The $\nu(\text{CN})$ at 2150 cm^{-1} and $\delta(\text{SCN})$ at 470 cm^{-1} found in the IR spectrum of $[\text{Pd}(\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$ also support sulphur bonding of thiocyanate group in triphenylstibine complexes⁸.

Experimental

Palladium(II) and platinum(II) chloride were obtained from Johnson Methew, London and other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The ligand triphenylphosphine sulphide⁹ and triphenylstibine sulphide¹⁰ were prepared as reported earlier. The diacido complexes, $[\text{ML}_2\text{X}_2]$ $\{\text{M} = \text{Pd}^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+} and $\text{L} = (\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{P}=\text{S}$ or $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{Sb}$ and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$ or $\text{SCN}\}$ were prepared by interaction of appropriate ligand in ethanol or methanol and aqueous ethanolic solution of metal chloride in 2 : 1 molar proportion. The diiodo, dithiocyanato or dibromo complexes $[\text{ML}_2\text{Cl}_2]$ with an excess of potassium salt of appropriate anion. The stibine complexes $[\text{M}\{(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{Sb}\}_2\text{X}_2]$ $(\text{M} = \text{Pd}^{2+}$ or Pt^{2+} and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{I}^-$ or $\text{SCN})$ were isolated on desulphurization of $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{SbS}$ in ethanolic medium with Pd^{II} or Pt^{II} . The complexes were filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried over CaCl_2 . The results of C/H correspond with calculated result.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to CDRI, Lucknow, USIC, Delhi University, JMI, New Delhi and BHU, Varanasi for re-

cording IR, UV, NMR and elemental analysis. The authors are also very much thankful to Dr. L. K. Mishra Retired Professor, Department of Chemistry, Science College, Patna, Dr. A. K. Ghosh, Department of Chemistry, Science College, Patna, and Dr. Sheo Satya Prakash, Department of Chemistry, A. N. College, Patna, for their kind cooperation and constant encouragement.

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